

Weights Behavior in the Solution Space of the Cerebellar Model Articulation Controller (CMAC) learning

Muhamad Iradat Achmad¹⁾, Adhi Susanto²⁾, Hanung Adinugroho³⁾
 Department of Electrical and Information Technology, Universitas Gadjah Mada
¹⁾iradat@ymail.com, ³⁾adinugroho@ugm.ac.id

Abstract

CMAC is an artificial neural network which represents the cerebellum model. This network has the capability to learn fast and to store information locally. The important aspect of learning capability is weights convergence. In line with that, this paper presents weights behavior in the solution space of CMAC learning. First, CMAC learning was formulated into the least square problem. Second, the least square solutions including LU, QR, and SVD methods were examined. Third, the LMS algorithm of CMAC learning was presented to compute the least square solution iteratively. In the implementation, sequential image "Claire" were used to arrange the dataset in which the row, column, and frame numbers are the network input and the corresponding pixel value is the desired output. Results show that the LMS solution with zero weights initialization converges to the SVD solution. The order of methods based on the norm values from smallest to largest are SVD, LMS, QR, and LU respectively. In the solution space, the LU, QR, and LMS weights with random initialization are segmented into subspaces based on CMAC generalization values. Weights on the same subspace have a uniform distance to the corresponding SVD subspace. In addition, the speed and stability of the weight training influenced by the convergence parameter μ in which the higher the value of μ , the faster the speed of weight convergence, and the more erratic the weight convergence tracking.

Keywords—CMAC learning, least square problem, weights behavior, solution space

I. INTRODUCTION

Cerebellar model articulation controller (CMAC) is an artificial neural network that imitates the cerebellum model [1][2]. This network has capability to learn fast and to store information locally. The important aspect of learning capability is weights convergence. Related to this, Wong and Sideris show that the learning process always converges with arbitrary accuracy on any set of training data [3]. Lin and Chiang use a mathematic formulation to show that the learning process converges in a finite iteration cycle [4]. Weights convergence is also related to weights behavior in the solution space in which other solutions exist. This paper examines weights behavior in more detail and refers to CMAC structure [5] in implementation.

Specific applications of CMAC such as hierarchical image coding [6] and image compression [7] need not only the convergent state of the learning process but also redundancy and distribution of weight values that potentially exploited to increase the coding performance. For this purposes, the effect of weights initialization, dynamics of

weights toward convergent, the effect of convergent parameter, the relationship between the structure and the final weights, and the final solution across a wide range of possible solutions in the solution space are significant information for further investigation in this paper.

This paper systematically arranged as follows. After introduction in the first section, the CMAC learning process is formulated to be the least square problem in the second section. The third section explains least square solutions including LU, QR, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), and Least Mean Square (LMS) methods. The implementation section contains dataset, results, and discussions. The last section containing conclusions and suggestions ends this paper.

II. THE LEAST SQUARE PROBLEM OF THE CMAC LEARNING

CMAC learning is a mechanism to store information of input output relationship into a set of weights. The mechanism applied on a training dataset contains a number of data pair, $\{a_i, y_i\}$, $i=1, \dots, N$. In this case, a_i is the i^{th} input association vector, y_i is desired output, i is data presentation number in training, and N is the amount of training data. The j^{th} element of a_i has non zero value only if the corresponding basis function triggered by CMAC input. $j=1, \dots, p$ is the weight element number and p is the amount of weights. If a set of weights expressed in column vector as w , then the problem of CMAC learning is to compute $w_j \in w$ so that the equation

$$a_i^T w = y_i \quad (1)$$

apply for all $i=1, \dots, N$. T is transpose operator. In complete dataset, $N \gg p$ so that (1) in matrix form become

$$Aw = y \quad (2)$$

where A is the input association matrix with number of rows is greater than number of columns. Equation (2) is known as the least square problem and solution $w=w^*$ be the approximate solution such that the sum of square error

$$e^T e = (Aw^* - y)^T (Aw^* - y) \quad (3)$$

is smallest. e is an error vector.

III. LEAST SQUARE SOLUTIONS

Least square solutions of problem (2) can be obtained through several methods including LU, QR, SVD, and LMS methods. These methods are explained in the following section.

A. The LU method

Most of the algorithms for computing LU methods are variants of Gaussian elimination technique [8]. In this technique, Gauss matrix is defined as

$$G_i = I + m_i e_i^T \tag{4}$$

with $m_k=0$ for $k \leq i$. It can be proven that the inverse of Gauss matrix in (3) is

$$G_i = I - m_i e_i^T \tag{5}$$

Using (4) and (5), LU method is applied to the autocorrelation of input association matrix $A^T A$ as bellow

$$(G_1^{-1} G_2^{-1} G_3^{-1} \dots G_{p-1}^{-1}) (G_{p-1} \dots G_3 G_2 G_1 A^T A) = LU \tag{6}$$

where $L = G_1^{-1} G_2^{-1} G_3^{-1} \dots G_p^{-1}$ is a lower triangular matrix

with a unit diagonal and $U = G_p \dots G_3 G_2 G_1 A^T A$ is an upper triangular matrix. Pre-multiplying A^T applied to both side of (2) changes the problem into p -by- p system known as normal equation

$$(A^T A)w = A^T y \tag{7}$$

Solution of LU method is obtained by applying (6) to (7) so

$$Lv = z \tag{8}$$

and then

$$Uw = v \tag{9}$$

where $z = A^T y$. The resulting triangular system (9) is ready for back substitution.

B. The QR method

The QR method is an orthogonalization algorithm that widely used to solve (2). The letter ‘‘Q’’ is a substitute for the letter ‘‘O’’ in ‘‘orthogonal’’ and the letter ‘‘R’’ is for ‘‘right’’ triangular matrix. This method performs orthogonalization by applying a sequence of Householder reflections to the column of A to produce the matrix R [9].

$$H_p H_{p-1} \dots H_3 H_2 H_1 A = R \tag{10}$$

The j^{th} column of R is a linear combination of the first j columns of A . Consequently, the elements of R below the main diagonal are zero. The matrix Q in (10) is implicitly equals to $H_p H_{p-1} \dots H_3 H_2 H_1$. Applying the same sequence to right side of (2) changes the problem into

$$Rw = z \tag{11}$$

where $z = H_p H_{p-1} \dots H_3 H_2 H_1 y$. The triangular system (11) can be solved for w by back substitution.

C. The SVD method

SVD is a particularly revealing complete orthogonal decomposition [10]. It is based on a theorem from linear algebra which says that a rectangular matrix A can be transformed into a diagonal matrix S by pre-multiplying it with the transpose of an orthogonal matrix U and post-multiplying it with an orthogonal matrix V . The theorem is usually presented as

$$U^T A V = S \tag{12}$$

where $S = \text{diag}(s_i)$ is a diagonal matrix with $s_i \in S, i=1, \dots, p$, is the i^{th} singular value. The least square problem (2) can be solved by $w = w^*$ so it minimizes

$$\|e\|_2 = \|Aw^* - y\|_2 \tag{13}$$

Applying (12) to (13) and using the orthogonal property of V change the 2-norm equation of (13) into

$$\begin{aligned} \|Aw^* - y\|_2 &= \|(U^T S V)(V^T w^*) - U^T y\|_2 \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^r (s_i \alpha_i - u_i^T y)^2 + \sum_{i=r+1}^p u_i^T y \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where $\alpha = V^T w^*$ and $r = \text{rank}(A)$. Clearly, if w^* solves the least square problem, then $\alpha_i = u_i^T y / s_i$ for $i=1, \dots, r$. Thus, the solution of (2) is obtained by

$$w^* = \sum_{i=1}^r \frac{u_i^T y}{s_i} v_i \tag{15}$$

where $r \leq p$. If $\alpha_i = 0, i=r+1, \dots, p$, then the resulting w^* clearly has minimal 2-norm.

D. The LMS method

LMS is the default method of CMAC learning. This method performs three sequential steps, namely output calculating, error calculating, and weights updating, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Output in the k^{th} step is

Figure 1. Illustration of the LMS method.

$$\hat{y}_k = \sum_{i=1}^p a_{i,k} w_{i,k} \quad (16)$$

and it causes an error

$$e_k = y_k - \hat{y}_k \quad (17)$$

Estimation of the performance function $\xi_k = E[e_k^2] \cong e_k^2$ used to predicts an instant gradient in the k^{th} step and the convergent parameter μ are used to update weights as below.

$$w_{k+1} = w_k - \mu \nabla(e_k^2) \quad (18)$$

Gradient operator in (18) is defined as a column vector

$$\nabla(\bullet) = \left[\frac{\partial(\bullet)}{\partial w_{1,k}} \quad \frac{\partial(\bullet)}{\partial w_{2,k}} \quad \dots \quad \frac{\partial(\bullet)}{\partial w_{p,k}} \right]^T \quad (19)$$

and the i^{th} element of (19) is

$$\frac{\partial(e_k^2)}{\partial w_{i,k}} = 2e_k \frac{\partial e_k}{\partial w_{i,k}} \quad (20)$$

Substituting (17) into the last factor of (20) and referring to the fact that y_k is independent against $w_{i,k}$ can change (20) into

$$\frac{\partial(e_k^2)}{\partial w_{i,k}} = -2e_k \frac{\partial \hat{y}_k}{\partial w_{i,k}} \quad (21)$$

By using (16), (21) can be formulated as

$$\frac{\partial(e_k^2)}{\partial w_{i,k}} = -2e_k a_{i,k} \quad (21)$$

and the expression of gradient vector in (19) becomes

$$\nabla(e_k^2) = -2e_k a_k \quad (22)$$

Applying the gradient vector of (22) into (18) produces

$$w_{k+1} = w_k + 2\mu e_k a_k \quad (23)$$

which is well known as the LMS method. Equation (23) shows that weights updating is always parallel with input.

After adaptation in the k^{th} step, network output can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} y_k^+ &= a_k^T w_k = a_k^T (w_{k-1} + 2\mu e_k a_k) \\ &= a_k^T w_{k-1} + 2\mu a_k^T a_k (\hat{y}_k - y_k) a_k \\ &= y_k + 2\mu a_k^T a_k \hat{y}_k - 2\mu a_k^T a_k y_k \\ &= 2\mu a_k^T a_k \hat{y}_k + (1 - 2\mu a_k^T a_k) y_k, \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

and error that occurs is

$$\begin{aligned} e_k^+ &= \hat{y}_k^+ - y_k^+ \\ &= \hat{y}_k^+ - 2\mu a_k^T a_k \hat{y}_k - (1 - 2\mu a_k^T a_k) y_k \\ &= (1 - 2\mu a_k^T a_k) \hat{y}_k - (1 - 2\mu a_k^T a_k) y_k \\ &= (1 - 2\mu a_k^T a_k) (\hat{y}_k - y_k) \\ &= (1 - 2\mu a_k^T a_k) e_k. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Reduction of error occurs if the convergent parameter μ is in interval

$$0 < \mu < \frac{1}{2a_k^T a_k}. \quad (26)$$

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation in this section uses a dataset arranged from the sequential image data "Claire" [11] shown in Fig. 2. In the dataset, spatio-temporal positions (row, column, and frame numbers) are used to be input and the corresponding gray level values are used to be output. The dataset is applied on CMAC [5] with generalization $g=5$ and displacement vector $d=[1,2,4]$.

Figure 2. Sequential image data "Claire".

Fig. 3 shows the LU, QR, and SVD solutions. The LMS solution in magenta line is also shown on its initialization values. The LU solution in blue line looks to have the widest range of values. It followed by the QR solution in green line that has a lower range of values and the SVD solution in red line gives the lowest range values. The LMS solution still needs to start iteration. This visual observation becomes more convincing after the 2-Norm calculation of solutions that puts SVD as the smallest, followed by QR, and then LU as the biggest. The $A^T A$ operation in LU method is always more badly conditioned than the original overdetermined system A in (2). Although the Gauss technique of LU method avoids the inverse operation of $A^T A$ so the solution accuracy increased, but the QR method that uses the vertical orthogonalization technique in (10) to reduce the column dependency of A provides better solution than LU. However, the SVD method that applies two ways orthogonalization in both vertical and horizontal direction in (12) gives the best solution.

The dynamics of weight elements in the solution space are not quite visible in Fig. 3. Subtracting each solution by SVD produces visual enhancement given in Fig. 4. This figure clearly shows that the elements of the LU and QR

solutions have exactly the same value changes with the elements of the SVD solution. Each of LU and QR solutions is divided into several subspaces and intended changes occur in the subspaces that are formed. The formed subspaces number is determined by the generalization parameter of CMAC, which in this case $g=5$. This parameter causes the CMAC structure has five overlapped layers. In each layer, a number of basis functions are arranged in such so no basis functions in different layer have exactly the same input coverage area. The sifting process is applied to a basis function to get a value corresponding to the trigger input. The sifting values are then loaded into the matrix A based on

the direction of input scanning, so each row of the matrix contains five non-zero elements that each distance is equal to the number of basis functions in the corresponding layer, and adjacent inputs will be mapped to the adjacent rows.

Fig. 5 displays the LMS solution on epoch-787 in the solution space where LU, QR, and SVD solutions are also located. The LMS solution is obtained by the weight updating of (18) with $\mu=0.02$ and $w_0=0$. Starting from the first training data $\{a_1, y_1\}$, the LMS method computes weights in the first iteration w_1 . For dataset with N training data pairs, the LMS takes N iterations to compute w_N and

Figure 3. The LU (blue), QR (green), and SVD (red) solutions, and the initialization value of the LMS solution (magenta).

Figure 4. Visual enhancement of Fig. 3 by subtracting the SVD weights from each of solutions

Figure 5. The LMS solution with zero initialization weights (magenta) tends to converge to the SVD solution.

Figure 6. The LMS solution with random initialization weights (magenta) converges to a solution that is different from other solutions.

finish the first epoch. After 787 epochs, the LMS solution with zero initialization tends to converge to the SVD solution. A different situation is shown in Fig. 6 in which the LMS iteration with random initialization converges to a subspace that is different from other solutions. In the solution space, weights in a subspace may be expressed as $c\eta$ where c is a constant and η is a null vector of SVD. The value c represents the distance between a solution subspace and the corresponding SVD subspace. Clearly, in Fig. 5, if a solution has c values denoted as $\{c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5\}$ then the sum of c_i for all i is equal to zero.

Fig. 7 displays the change in the Euclidean norm (EN) of the solution from LMS to SVD. In the first ten epochs shown on the left of Fig. 7, the EN of LMS looks like a damped oscillation curve and approaches the EN of SVD from below. The curve crosses the EN of SVD in epoch 177 and keeps heading up (see the middle of Fig. 7). The EN curve of LMS tends to be stabilized in epoch 700 and stays in above of SVD with different values around 0.61. This is shown in the right of Fig. 7. The EN is calculated by summing the squares of all weight elements and taking the square root. In the first epoch, the EN calculation produces the largest value because the difference between the network target and the network output in (17) is large enough so that its uniform distribution in (23) yields the large ranges of weight values. In addition to that, the internal mechanism of CMAC explains that the neighboring inputs will be mapped to the overlapping weights so that a large different of the neighboring desired outputs will significantly increase the difference of weight updating values. However, in the next epoch, the weight updating values will be continuously

decreased because the knowledge has been stored in the weights.

Fig. 8 displays changes in the value of LMS weights from its zero initialization to the corresponding SVD weights. The step size between successive epochs appears increasingly smaller as the value of LMS elements are close to SVD. The largest step size that occurs in the first epoch is also a justification for the related discussion of the norm curve previously. If it is assumed that the performance surface exists as a function of the p -dimensional weights and the SVD solution be the point in the lowest valley, then the LMS weights move down the valley towards the SVD point in which the mean square error decreases to the lowest level. The gradient vector (22) uses the square error of the k^{th} iteration e_k^2 as an estimate of the performance function ξ_k to compute an instant gradient at the k^{th} iteration. This imperfect gradient estimate causes the weight updating to be noisy and it will not follow a straight line from the initial point to the SVD point as it shown in both left and right of Fig. 8.

Fig. 9 displays the effect of the convergence parameter μ to the speed and stability of the weight updating in the CMAC learning. The speed of convergence seems to be increase as μ increase. In the left of Fig. 9, with $\mu=0.001$, the CMAC learning has been running as far as 968 epochs, but the SVD target is still quite far away. The higher speed is given by $\mu=0.05$ in the middle of Fig. 9 (and also by $\mu=0.02$ in the left of Fig. 8) in which the weight elements are closer to the target although the learning process just runs for 57 epochs. The very high speed is given by CMAC learning

Figure 7. The EN curve of the LMS solution looks like a damped oscillation in the first ten epochs (left), crosses the SVD curve in around of epoch 180 (middle), and converges above the SVD curve in epoch 760 (right).

Figure 8. Changes in the 100th, 1000th (left), 33th, and 768th (right) of the LMS weights from its zero initialization to the corresponding SVD weights.

Figure 9. The effect of the convergence parameter μ to the speed and stability of the weight updating in the CMAC learning. (left) $\mu=0.001$, epoch=968, (middle) $\mu=0.05$, epoch=57, and (right) $\mu=0.08$, epoch=37.

with $\mu=0.08$ in the right of Fig. 9. It only takes 37 epochs to make the weight elements are very close to the target. Furthermore, the visual inspection of Fig. 8 shows that the stability of the weights updating is also affected by the value of μ . The smaller μ gives the smoother weight tracking, while the higher μ produces the more erratic weight behavior.

V. CONCLUSION

Weights behavior in the solution space of the CMAC learning had been presented. Starting from the CMAC learning represented into the least square problem, the methods of LU, QR, and SVD are examined to solve the problem. The LMS method as the default algorithm of the CMAC learning is then presented to solve the problem iteratively. After arranging the sequential image "Claire" as the learning dataset, the proposed methods are applied to obtain the LU, QR, SVD, and LMS weights. In the solution space, the LMS method with zero weights initialization converges to the SVD solution. Solutions of LU, QR, and LMS with random initialization are segmented into subspaces based on the CMAC generalization. Weights in each subspace are uniformly distributed and have equal distance to the corresponding SVD subspaces. The sequence of methods that gives norm values from smallest to largest are SVD, LMS, QR, and LU. The speed and stability of the weight convergence are influenced by the convergence parameter μ in which the higher the value of μ , the faster the speed of weight convergence, and the more erratic the weight convergence tracking.

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